

**LINGUODIDACTIC FUNDAMENTALS OF FORMING
PHRASEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN TEACHING
THE KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE****Nurimbetova Sarbinaz Keunimjay kizi**

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ABSTRACT

This thesis highlights the linguodidactic foundations for developing students' phraseological competence in teaching the Karakalpak language. The importance of phraseological units in language and speech, methods of their teaching, and ways of forming competence based on modern pedagogical technologies are analyzed. The effectiveness of communicative, interactive, and reflexive approaches in developing phraseological competence is also demonstrated.

Today, training specialists based on a competency-based approach is one of the most pressing issues in the education system. In particular, in philological education, it is important to develop students' skills in the appropriate and meaningful use of language units. From this perspective, teaching the phraseological richness of the Karakalpak language and forming students' phraseological competence is one of the important directions of linguodidactics.

Phraseological units enhance the imagery of speech as a linguistic phenomenon reflecting the national thinking, culture, lifestyle, and worldview of a people. Developing students' ability to understand, analyze, and use phraseological units in practical speech strengthens their communicative competence.

In linguodidactics, phraseological competence is understood as students' knowledge of the meaning, structure, stylistic features, and function of phraseological units in speech, as well as their ability to use them correctly in communicative situations. Phraseological competence is a component of language competence and is closely related to speech activity.

When teaching phraseological units in the Karakalpak language, it is necessary to adhere to several linguodidactic principles:

- systematicity and consistency;
- communicativeness;
- national-cultural approach;
- activity-oriented education;
- integrative approach.

In the process of developing phraseological competence, students are first explained the semantic features of phraseological units. For example, phrases such as "kózi jalt etiw", "júregi

suv ete qalıw", "tili qısqa bolıw" differ from simple phrases in that they are used in a figurative sense. Teaching such units based on context allows for a deeper understanding of their content.

The use of interactive methods in teaching phraseological units yields effective results.

Including:

- cluster;
- brainstorming;
- debate;
- role play;
- situational exercises;
- methods of phraseological analysis.

These methods help develop students' independent thinking and introduce phraseological units into active speech. In particular, through dialogue and work in small groups, students practically master the stylistic possibilities of expressions.

The use of modern educational technologies also plays an important role in the development of phraseological competence. Electronic platforms, multimedia tools, phraseological dictionaries, and digital assignments increase students' interest. For example, explaining phraseological units through visual metaphors increases their retention rate.

Also, classes organized on the basis of a reflexive approach teach students to evaluate their speech. During the reflection process, students determine which phraseological units they used correctly or incorrectly and analyze their speech deficiencies. This contributes to the gradual formation of phraseological competence. The national-cultural component is also important in the development of phraseological competence. This is because the customs, values, and historical experience of the Karakalpak people are embodied in phraseological units. For this reason, the study of phraseological units on an ethnolinguistic basis is of great importance for students.

In conclusion, the development of phraseological competence in the Karakalpak language is one of the urgent issues of linguodidactics. Effective teaching of phraseological units develops students' speech culture, communicative literacy, and creative thinking skills. The educational process, organized on the basis of interactive methods, a communicative approach and modern pedagogical technologies, ensures high efficiency in the formation of phraseological competence. Therefore, the systematic and purposeful use of phraseological materials in Karakalpak language lessons is of great scientific and practical importance.

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